

SPATIAL PROCESSING OF SOUND IN MPEG-4 VIRTUAL WORLDS

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ABSTRACT

MPEG-4 is a standard for interactive multimedia applications, where tools are specified for presenting sound in 3-D virtual scenes. This includes parametric representations of 3-D sound source models and the environment where the sound is heard. This article gives an overview on how interactive sound environments are parametrized in the scene description language of MPEG-4. Furthermore, DSP issues for the implementation of the acoustic environment are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

MPEG-4 is an ISO/IEC standard that specifies coding and object-based presentation of audio and visual content, aiming at interactive multimedia applications, and streaming delivery of data in low-bandwidth and error prone delivery channels [1, 2]. MPEG-4 allows not only playing of decoded sound, but also composition of sound tracks out of several elementary streams that may be encoded using different audio coding methods, and possibly transmitted from different servers to the decoding terminal. In addition, composed audio tracks can be presented in a 3-D virtual scene, placed in a position defined in a scene description language called *Binary Format for Scene Description*, BIFS, defined in the Systems part of the standard [3].

The first version of MPEG-4 that reached an International Standard status in 1999, enables simple 3-D sound source object presentation similar to that in the Virtual Reality Modeling Language (VRML) sound source model [4]. However, in the second version of the standard (to be technically finalized in 2000), enhanced modeling of an acoustic environment is made possible: A virtual scene and the sound sources placed in it can be given advanced acoustic properties that are derived from the *physical* or *perceptual* definition of room acoustic features (described in more detail in the following section). For example, a room with reflecting or sound obstructing walls can be specified to give a natural impression of a reverberating space, or speed of sound can be defined in order to simulate propagation delay of a

sound and the respective Doppler effect when relative motion occurs between the source and the listener [5, 6]. All the sound environment parameters are defined in BIFS which is transmitted as part of the MPEG-4 content, and the processing of sound according to those parameters is carried out locally at the terminal. This article discusses the parametric, object-based presentation of virtual acoustic environments in MPEG-4 BIFS, and the corresponding audio processing that is required to make these parameters audible to the viewer of the MPEG-4 content. First we present the general concepts of MPEG-4 and the audio tools included in the standard. Then a detailed description is given about the audio processing that is required to make audible the spatial properties given in the scene description.

2 AUDIO CONCEPTS AND TOOLS IN MPEG-4

MPEG-4 features methods for coding of natural and synthetic audiovisual objects. As such, a single MPEG-4 stream may consist of several different elementary stream objects each of which can be encoded with different coding methods, e.g., with a CELP speech encoder, general audio (GA) encoder, or a natural video encoder. These streams are *composed* and finally played to the user at the MPEG-4 terminal (decoder), once decoded with the corresponding decoders. In addition to the general concept of object and source-based coding of data, MPEG-4 defines techniques for encoding of *synthetic* data. The synthetic coding means computer-based generation of audio and visual data according to parametric descriptions of the source object (e.g., physical model of a music instrument), and adding of time-dependent control information for actually “playing” the source. The audio part of the standard includes two different coding methods for synthetic audio, namely the *Structured Audio* (SA) coding, and a *Text-To-Speech Interface* (TTSI) [7]. Both methods allow transmission of audio at very low bitrates targeting for usage over low-bandwidth data channels. The parametric control of the sound also enables flexible interactive playing of sounds. Together

the audio composition and synthetic audio coding are referred to as *Synthetic Audio Tools* in MPEG-4 [8, 7].

The composition process of MPEG-4 data includes the actual presentation of the streams according to the spatial and temporal information given in BIFS. Thus, the streaming objects can be designed to represent real world objects that are the sources of sound, such as a speaking person, or visual data, such as an object containing a video sprite of the person talking. BIFS allows assigning of sound objects spatially with visual objects so that the sound appears to come from the position of the visible source of sound. *AudioBIFS* is the part in MPEG-4 Systems version 1 that defines how an audio track is formed out of several audio elementary streams, defines the spatio-temporal presentation of sound to the user, and enables addition of post-processing effects to any MPEG-4 audio tracks [9]. The mixing and post-processing of sounds to form a single audible track is characterized as traditional audio *content composition*, whereas the spatial presentation is referred to as *Virtual Reality composition* where acoustic 3-D space is created (see, [1], Systems part). *Advanced AudioBIFS*, included in the MPEG-4 version 2, is an extension to *AudioBIFS* that allows more advanced Virtual Reality (VR) composition, i.e., modeling of spatial presentation of sound sources in 3-D BIFS scenes. This means that sound sources and associated objects are given acoustic properties as a set of parameters that are taken into account in the sound processing before the source is presented, or made audible to the user. The sound is given a position in a 3-D coordinate system of the terminal, and the location of the sound as well as the effect of the surrounding acoustic environment should be heard and change dynamically when any of the acoustic factors change (positions of the source or the listener, or the position of objects causing acoustic response such as sound reflections or obstruction).

It should also be noted that MPEG-4 *AudioBIFS* and *Advanced AudioBIFS*, like VRML audio scene description, do not specify any specific methods for audio processing and playback in the terminal. Different methods for positional audio such as binaural, crosstalk canceled, or multichannel techniques as well as reverberation algorithms can be utilized, but it is up to the MPEG-4 player implementer to make decisions on the use of such approaches and the choice of algorithms. In addition, the data needed for presentation such as head-related transfer functions are not normative parts of the standard.

3 VIRTUAL ACOUSTIC ENVIRONMENT RENDERING

This section discusses the audio signal processing required for the Virtual Reality composition of sounds in *Advanced AudioBIFS*. Like any BIFS components, also those having acoustic relevance are represented by

node objects whose *fields* hold the information about the parameters defining the properties of the object. In *Advanced AudioBIFS* there are four nodes that define the acoustic events and behaviours of a virtual 3-D scene. These nodes are:

1. **DirectiveSound** used for advanced modeling of directive sound sources and acoustic environment.
2. **AcousticScene** used for defining areas in a 3-D scene where the sound is heard when both the source and the listener are in the same area. This node also allows associating to the same room acoustic modeling process several surfaces with acoustic properties.
3. **AcousticMaterial** used for attaching frequency dependent reflectivity or sound transmission properties to a polygonal surface.
4. **PerceptualParameters** used for associating a room acoustic response characterized by a set of perceptual attributes to one sound source.

In *Advanced AudioBIFS* there are two approaches to VR composition of sound. One is the *physical* approach where an acoustic effect is created according to the geometrical description of the acoustic environment (related to the visual VR world), and depends on the current positions and movements of the sound source and the listener. General modeling and audio signal processing aspects related to this approach are discussed in detail in [10]. The *perceptual* approach, on the other hand, tends to produce a high quality room acoustic effect that is controlled with a set of parameters associated with each sound source and is not necessarily related to the visual reality. These parameters describe relative, frequency dependent energies of different parts of the time-domain room response, and they are *source presence*, *source brilliance*, *source warmth*, *room presence*, *running reverberance*, *envelopment*, *late reverberance*, *heaviness*, and *liveness*, discussed in more detail in [11]. When a **PerceptualParameters** node is associated with a **DirectiveSound** node, the physical acoustic properties (such as reflectivity of polygons) bound to the visual 3-D environment are ignored in processing of that source. However, many of the properties related to the spatial sound processing are common to these two approaches. These include frequency dependent directivity modeling, distance dependent attenuation, propagation delay, late reverberation and rendering of direction of sound (listener modeling).

Figure 1 presents a general signal processing block diagram for producing a room acoustic effect for one sound source in both the physical and the perceptual approaches. It contains two delay lines one of which implements the direct sound delay, and the other the delays of the early reflections. Filters H_{input} and H_{Omni} are the input and omnidirectivity filters that can be defined in the **PerceptualParameters** [5]. In the physical

Figure 1: A common model for Digital Signal Processing unit for a single sound source in Advanced AudioBIFS.

approach the omnidirectivity filter is not defined and the same delay line can be used for the direct sound and early reflections. The direct sound delay line is fed with a monophonic source signal. Outputs are taken from the delay lines corresponding to the direct sound between the source and the listener, and to the early reflections, caused by the reflecting surfaces in the physical approach, or defined by values given in **PerceptualParameters** in the case of the perceptual approach. The direct sound and early reflections are processed with a set of filters depicted in more detail in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 1 gives an idea of the sound processing in a static situation, but also it should be noted that even if the processing blocks are much similar in the physical and the perceptual approaches, a dynamic situation is different: In the physical approach changes in the environment need to be tracked and updating the acoustic parameters (such as delays and directions of reflections) require more computation than the perceptual approach where they only depend on the relative positions of the source and the listener. The different filter blocks of Figures 2 and 3 are explained in context of the physical and perceptual approaches in Table 1.

It should be noted that when sound sources are included in a BIFS scene, all the afore-mentioned properties are not necessarily realized for each sound source. This means that the scene content author may define sources with different complexity requirements on the signal processing. For example, it may be desirable to have sources for which a room acoustic effect is produced, but also background sounds can be added that do not involve any processing, or only the spatialization of direct sound is rendered but no reverberation. The functionalities of the parameters (fields) in the Advanced AudioBIFS nodes are designed so that the different blocks in the sound processing are optional.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the spatial processing aspects of sound in the MPEG-4 standard were discussed. An overview of

Figure 2: Filters for modifying the direct sound.

Figure 3: Filters for obtaining the diffuse part of the room response. The diffuse early reflections are only defined in the perceptual approach.

MPEG-4 audio was given, and the Advanced AudioBIFS specification of MPEG-4 Systems for audio presentation was described in great detail.

The audio scene description part of the MPEG-4 standard (AudioBIFS and Advanced AudioBIFS) provides the most versatile set of audio presentation tools found in current multimedia specifications. Among the other standards for audiovisual scene description are VRML [4] and Java3D (for a more detailed summary, see [12]). The natural and synthetic audio coding tools combined with a set of nodes for presenting and post-processing the sound scene can be utilized in a wide variety of multimedia applications, both audiovisual and audio only.

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Sound processing block	Physical Approach	Perceptual Approach
Direct sound filters		
Distance	Includes distance dependent attenuation and air absorption modeling defined in DirectiveSound node.	Filter is dependent on the source presence, source brilliance and source warmth given in PerceptualParameters node. Also depends on the actual distance to the listener in the scene.
Directivity	Given in DirectiveSound node as frequency modifying filters, or frequency dependent gains for arbitrary number of angles with respect the main axis of source.	Same as in physical approach, but directivity can only be given as frequency dependent gains.
Obstruction	Filter given in AcousticMaterial node and applied when a polygon surface with AcousticMaterial appears in the direct path between the source and the listener.	Filter defined in PerceptualApproach node that can be applied to direct sound but does not depend on visual scene components.
Listener	Involves rendering of the direction of arrival of sound dependent on the relative positions of source and the listener. Processing is dependent on the reproduction method which is not defined in the standard.	Done similarly as in physical approach.
Early reflection filters		
Distance	Gain of each reflection dependent on the distance of the corresponding image source	Gain of each reflection dependent on the delay and running reverberance (corresponding to early decay time).
Reflectivity	Filtering separately for each early reflection, defined by reflectivity in AcousticSurface node.	Common filter for all reflections depending on source presence, source brilliance, and source warmth.
Listener	Direction of each reflection depends on the corresponding image source location, and is rendered according to the reproduction system used.	Directions of each reflection are pre-set, but move with the direction of the direct sound. Rendering done similarly as in the physical approach depending on the reproduction setup.
Diffuse response filters		
Diffuse early reflections		Diffuse, non-decaying part of the late response with a dense pattern of randomly distributed reflections. Total energy is defined in PerceptualParameters node.
Late reverberator	Reverberator with exponentially decaying response, whose frequency dependent decay time is controlled with the reverb definitions in AcousticScene node.	Same reverberator can be used as in physical approach, but response controlled by late reverberance, heavyness and liveness defined in PerceptualParameters node.

Table 1: Filtering modules shown in Figures 2 and 3, used for producing a room acoustic effect in the physical and perceptual approaches in BIFS.

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